

PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS IN THE LIFE OF MODERN SOCIETY

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Abstract. The article examines the role of physical culture and sports in the life of modern society. The positive role of physical activity on the functional state of the human body is noted. Sport as a prevention of deviant behavior in modern society.

Key words: health, physical culture and sports, healthy lifestyle Today, sport is an integral part of society. Permeating all levels of modern society, it has a great influence on the main spheres of society. Sport influences relationships at the national level, a person's position in society, thereby shaping fashion, ethical values, and people's lifestyles. In addition to preventing bad habits, physical culture satisfies the entertainment needs of humanity. In the 21st century, there is not a single person who is not involved in physical education and sports, who does not participate in any competitions, relay races, or flash mobs.

Proof of all the above points is that interest in major international competitions, such as the Olympic Games, World and European Championships, and World Universiade, is steadily growing. Every second inhabitant of the planet watches these competitions, because these are the most exciting and unpredictable spectacles. Watching the world's outstanding athletes, people receive a storm of emotions that are incomparable to anything else. Such major events attract people to engage in physical education and sports.

Physical education and sports solve a number of problems that have become very acute for modern society in the 21st century. This is inactivity, bad habits, deviant behavior.

Sports and physical culture play a significant role in the formation of personality. An athlete gains life experience due to the fact that many social situations are played out in sports.

Finding himself in a new social sphere, a sports section or school, a young athlete finds himself surrounded by elements of a new social sphere: coaches, judges, sports teams - these are specific people on whose shoulders the responsibility for upbringing and education, teaching cultural norms and behavior is entrusted, ensuring effective mastering and implementing a new social role. For each person, primary socialization plays a special role, in which the fundamental psychophysical and moral qualities of the individual are laid.

The social institute of physical culture and sports takes part in the primary socialization of the athlete simultaneously with the parents and the school. Among representatives of primary socialization, not everyone plays the same roles and has equal status. Among the agents of primary socialization, roles are distributed unevenly. Parents, in relation to the child, have a dominant position. In the relationship with a young athlete, the coach, like parents, has a significant influence, thereby strengthening the positions of the former. In the opposite direction from the coach and parents, the influence on the child is

exerted by his peers. When influencing an athlete, they forgive him much of what parents and coaches do not forgive. In our century, physical culture and sports are a multifunctional social phenomenon. First of all, this is directly related to the fact of its impact on a person's upbringing, as well as the prevention and reduction of the risk of a wide range of diseases. Physical education and sports on a regular basis lead to an increase in a person's functional capabilities, the activity of metabolic processes in the body, and the stabilization of metabolism and energy.

Otherwise, a sedentary lifestyle leads to muscle atrophy, decreased bone strength, and deterioration in the functional state of the central nervous, respiratory, cardiovascular and other systems. The tone and vital activity of the body is significantly reduced. Many doctors recommend sport as a preventive measure for many diseases, and physical activity has always been, is and will be the basis of rehabilitation after any illness, surgery, or injury. It is also recommended that absolutely all people, regardless of age, engage in cyclic sports (running, swimming, skiing).

These sports, when properly dosed, have a huge positive effect on the musculoskeletal system; when playing these sports, all muscle groups are involved in the work. Physical education increases stress resistance, which is important for modern society. But there is also another side of the coin, such as abuse of physical activity, which is especially noticeable in modern society.

Since the modern beauty industry dictates its own rules and people adapt to it, problems arise with understanding what physical activity is. Many desperately spend hours in gyms, running grueling cross-country races, without a fitness instructor or coach, thinking that reading on the Internet or asking a friend for his workout program will give a positive effect after a short period of time. Often this does not happen, because a person does not know his body's capabilities, does not know its functional state, and does not even imagine that through his ignorance he is causing great harm to his body.

Abuse of physical activity can cause significant harm, so when choosing a load, you need an individual approach, which can be found by a specialist in the field, in other words, a trainer, fitness instructor. But in the 21st century there is a serious problem for physical culture and sports - the outflow of qualified specialists, coaches and athletes abroad. This is due, on the one hand, to the high level of preparedness of our specialists, coaches and athletes, their demand at the global level, and on the other hand, to the lack of conditions for full-fledged work in our country. Improving not only physical and sports, but also moral, aesthetic, and intellectual education - all this is provided by sport. The health-improving and recreational function of sport has a positive impact on the functional capabilities of the human body, the effect of which is difficult to overestimate in childhood and adolescence. Sports and physical education are especially important not only for children and young people, but also for older people. Physical activity slows down the aging process and also prevents a number of age-related diseases such as arthritis, arthrosis, hypertension, etc.

But it should be understood that physical activity, exercises, their intensity, systematicity depend on the age stage and its characteristics.

This system in new conditions is designed to solve problems of human development and the main attention is directed not only to the general problems of the entire population, but also to an individual approach to each person. Our state pays great attention and tries to

involve more and more people in sports. For this purpose, discounted visits to sports sections and facilities are provided for various organizations.

Children's and youth sports schools are being built so that schoolchildren can have the opportunity to attend a variety of sections, and benefits are provided for pensioners to visit various sports facilities. Based on this, we can conclude that the state pays due attention to physical culture and sports and approaches each age category with full responsibility. But this is not enough to increase the physical activity of the entire population; what is important is the desire of the person himself to exercise and move as often as possible. Currently, modern society prefers to follow sports while lying on the couch, without making any effort.

A person undoubtedly relaxes emotionally when watching sports broadcasts, because he worries about his idol or team. In the 21st century, physical culture and sports have become a business in which modern society invests huge amounts of money. Having examined physical culture and sports from an economic point of view, we can see that the material investments of modern society in sports pay off tenfold. First of all, this is due to improved health and increased life expectancy. And only then with business and fame.

Also in sports activities, various specific relations of rivalry and community of individual athletes arise, between teams, organizers, sports referees, etc., which are one way or another included in the system of social relations that go beyond the scope of sports. In conclusion, we can say that physical culture and sports are gradually developing all over the world, and every day more and more people are becoming involved in sporting events and trying to participate in them.

Currently, our country is developing an active interest in a healthy lifestyle. In fact, we can say that a new social phenomenon is emerging in Kazakhstan, expressed in the acute economic interest of citizens in maintaining health as the basis for material well-being. It is necessary to preserve and restore the best traditions of the domestic physical education and sports movement and continue the search for new highly effective physical education, health and sports technologies aimed at maximizing the involvement of all segments of the population in active physical education and sports.

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